

1st SASPAM-SA Training on LWR-SMR Safety: From DBA to Severe accident – Phenomena, Experiments, Mitigation Strategies, and Code Application

Location: Sapienza Congress Center via Salaria 113, Rome, Italy

Date: October 16-17, 2025

Funded by
the European Union

SPONSORSHIP

The 1st SASPAM-SA Training on LWR-SMR Safety: From DBA to Severe accident – Phenomena, Experiments, Mitigation Strategies, and Code Application, is supported and hosted by Sapienza Università di Roma (Italy).

BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

Light water cooled Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) are gaining significant attention as a near-term nuclear technology option due to their inherent safety features, compact design, modular construction potential, and reduced capital and operational costs. These designs are largely based on proven large LWR technology, offering opportunities for rapid deployment while maintaining high safety standards.

The 1st SASPAM-SA training aims to contribute to the capacity building needed to support the future licensing and deployment of SMRs in Europe. The training brings together researchers, engineers, and students to deepen their understanding of SMR-specific safety aspects, with a focus on accident phenomenology, mitigation strategies, and the application of state-of-the-art computational tools. This training event is organized within the framework of the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA project and complements the broader dissemination and knowledge-transfer activities ongoing in the European and international SMR community.

SCOPE AND TECHNICAL CONTENT

The training is designed to provide a comprehensive introduction and hands-on insight into SMR-specific safety challenges, leveraging the findings from SASPAM-SA and related European research initiatives.

Key topics addressed include:

- Accident scenarios and relevant safety phenomena in LWR-SMRs;
- Comparison of safety approaches in SMRs versus large LWRs;
- Severe accident mitigation strategies including In-Vessel Melt Retention (IVMR);
- Use of existing experimental databases to inform SMR safety;
- Emergency Planning Zones (EPZ) and regulatory perspectives for SMRs;
- Application and demonstration of major computational tools (AC2, ASTEC, MAAP, MELCOR, containmentFOAM, etc.) used in the SASPAM-SA project for SMR safety analysis;
- Future perspectives for research and development in SMR safety and licensing support.

The agenda spans theoretical lectures and applied case studies, providing participants with both foundational knowledge and exposure to ongoing advanced research and practical tools.

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

The technical content of the workshop has been prepared by the Organizing Committee members:

Fabio GIANNETTI	UNIROMA1	Italy
Fulvio MASCARI	ENEA	Italy
Fabrizio GABRIELLI	KIT	Germany
Terttaliisa LIND	PSI	Switzerland
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ATTENTION PLEASE:

IMPORTANT DATE:

Registration deadline:

July 30, 2025

AGENDA

Day 1 – SMR Design, Safety, and Mitigation Strategies

Session 1: SMR Safety: Phenomena, Experiments and Mitigation Strategies

08:00 - 09:00 | Registration and Welcome

- Participant reception and overview of training objectives.

09:00 - 09:40 | SMR Overview and Main Characteristics (F. Mascari – ENEA)

- Key characteristics of SMRs and differences from large LWRs.
- Overview of main safety systems in SMRs and associated phenomena.

09:40 - 10:20 | Defence-in-Depth and Mitigation Strategies (F. Giannetti – UNIROMA1)

- Introduction to the five levels of DiD and their application to SMRs.
- Mitigation strategies in SMRs compared to large reactors.

10:20 - 10:50 | Coffee Break

10:50 - 11:30 | Scenarios in SMRs (F. Gabrielli – KIT)

- Postulated scenarios in design and design extension condition for SMRs.
- First outcomes from the SASPAM-SA project.

11:30 - 12:10 | Key Experiments from Large Reactors and Applicability to SMRs (T. Lind – PSI)

- Review of key experimental data from large LWRs.
- Applicability of these experiments for SMR based on SASPAM-SA outcomes.

12:10 - 12:50 | In-Vessel Melt Retention (IVMR) in Large Reactors and SMRs (F. Fichot – ASNR)

- IVMR strategies in large reactors and differences in SMRs.
- State-of-the-art computational tools for IVMR assessment in SMRs based on SASPAM-SA outcomes.

12:50 - 14:00 | Lunch Break

14:00 - 14:40 | Containment Phenomena in Large Reactors and SMRs (N. Reinke – GRS)

- Containment behavior in large reactors and differences in SMRs.
- Application of computational tools for SMR containment analysis based on SASPAM-SA outcomes.

14:40 - 15:20 | Emergency Planning Zones (EPZ) for SMRs (M. Ilvonen – VTT)

- Regulatory framework and safety implications for EPZ in SMRs.
- Role of computational tools in EPZ evaluation based on SASPAM-SA outcomes.

15:20 - 15:45 | Coffee Break

Session 2: Computational Tools and Applications

15:45 - 16:15 | Introduction to Computational Tools for Severe Accident Analysis (F. Mascari - ENEA)

- Overview of computational tools used for severe accident analysis in SMRs.
- Key applications in the SASPAM-SA project.

16:00 - 16:45 | ASTEC and its Application in SASPAM-SA (L. Carenini ASNR + partners)

- Introduction to ASTEC software for safety analysis.
- Case studies in SASPAM-SA generic designs.

16:45 - 17:30 | AC2 and its Application in SASPAM-SA (N. Reinke GRS (TBC) + partners)

- Introduction to AC2 software for safety analysis.
- Case studies in SASPAM-SA generic designs.

17:30 - 18:00 | Q&A and Closing Remarks

- Summary of key takeaways from the training.
- Open discussion and participant feedback.

Day 2 – Computational Tools and Future Perspectives

08:30 - 09:15 | MELCOR and its Applications in SMR Safety (*F. Giannetti, UNIROMA1 + partners*)

- Introduction to MELCOR software for safety analysis.
- Case studies in SASPAM-SA generic designs.

09:15 - 10:00 | MAAP and MAAP-EDF: Applications in SMR Safety (*J. Bittan - EDF, J.C. De La Rosa Blul, JRC*)

- Introduction to MAAP software for safety analysis.
- Case studies in SASPAM-SA generic designs.

10:00 - 10:30 | Coffee Break

10:30 - 11:00 | CFD Applications in Severe Accident Analysis (*M. Pellegrini - POLIMI*)

- Role of CFD Large reactor for safety analysis.
- Case studies and modeling challenges for SMR.

11:00 - 11:45 | containmentFOAM: From large dry to SMR containment analysis with using a tailored CFD package (*S. Kelm, C. Vázquez-Rodríguez - FZJ*)

- Introduction to ContainmentFoam software for safety analysis.
- Case studies in SASPAM-SA generic design.

11:45 - 12:30 | Modelling of iPWR SMR Containment Behavior with ANSYS CFX (*M. Makarenko - SSTC*)

- Introduction to CFX software for safety analysis.
- Case studies in SASPAM-SA generic design.

12:30 - 13:00 | Future Perspectives and Conclusions (*F. Mascari – ENEA*)

- Summary of training outcomes and research priorities.
- Open discussion on future directions for experimental and computational studies.

13:00 - 13:30 | Closure and Certificate Distribution

- Final remarks and participant certification.

